

REINFORCING THE SPEAKING SKILLS OF STUDENTS AT THE B1-B2 LEVELS

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Annotation: This article focuses on methodologies aimed at improving the speaking skills of B1-B2 level English speakers. Considering theories of second language acquisition (SLA) and recent empirical researches thoroughly, it suggests a comprehensive framework prioritizing fluency development, vocabulary enhancement, and practical application. Specific attention is paid to the roles of pronunciation, constructive feedback, and technological integration in training self-confident communicators. The article also outlines research-based, practical activities designed to address the specific challenges and opportunities encountered by intermediate learners.

Keywords: Speaking skill, fluency, second language acquisition, intermediate learners, pronunciation, communicative activities, feedback.

Introduction

As speaking is one of the most dynamic and at the same time challenging aspects of language learning it requires learners to integrate linguistic knowledge, perceptive skills, and social interaction instantly. For B1-B2 level learners, this challenge intensifies as they shift from basic language use to complex communication. Speakers must accomplish fluency while maintaining accuracy and navigating contextual distinctions.

Krashen (1982) emphasizes the importance of comprehensible input for language acquisition, nonetheless Swain's (2005) Output Hypothesis underscores the need for learners to produce language actively. As a productive skill, speaking allows students to improve their understanding of grammar and vocabulary through immediate usage. Moreover, Vygotsky's (1978) Zone of Proximal Development highlights how guidance and scaffolding can facilitate learning, particularly for learners who require structured support to reach the next stage of proficiency.

This article studies the theoretical foundations of speaking skills development and proposes practical strategies for encouraging intermediate learners. These strategies intend to balance fluency, vocabulary growth, pronunciation and active listening while boosting learners' self-confidence.

Speaking skill advancement: challenges and prospects

Intermediate learners frequently come across a “stagnation” in their speaking development and they often feel limited, experience lack of vocabulary, struggle with accurate pronunciation, or hesitate to speak owing to anxiety of making mistakes. Jenkins (2000) points out that focusing on intelligibility rather than native-sounding pronunciation helps learners prioritize effective communication. Likewise, Nation (2013) notes that fluency exercises can enhance the speed and natural flow of language use, addressing the common difficulty with spontaneity.

Listening plays a vital role in developing speaking skills because listening to authentic materials such as podcasts, interviews or natural dialogues actively sharpens learners' ability to interpret and reply to conversational signals. Field (2008) states that listening skills form the basis for effective spoken interaction, as they help learners predict meaning and express appropriate responses. These challenges present a chance for teachers to design engaging, learner-centred activities that integrate speaking with other skills, while practical exposure, paired with targeted feedback, can help learners overcome these obstacles and build confidence.

Fluency and vocabulary expansion

One of the primary purposes for B1-B2 learners is attaining fluency. Fluency does not require perfection but rather the ability to express ideas coherently and naturally. Encouraging students to prioritize communication over grammatical accuracy can reduce anxiety and foster confidence. For instance, timed speaking activities like quick debates or storytelling can prompt spontaneous responses, aiding learners focus on conveying meaning rather than form.

Vocabulary expansion is at the same level critical. Intermediate learners benefit from mastering practical language and lexical chunks that happen in normal communication. Thornbury (2002) highlights that teaching collocations and situational phrases qualifies learners to speak both more naturally and spontaneously. Activities such as word maps or phrase-building exercises can support students internalize patterns, making their speech more organised and expressive.

The role of pronunciation and intonation

Pronunciation has an important role in intelligibility. It involves not only articulating sounds correctly but also mastering stress, rhythm, and intonation to

convey meaning successfully. For example, the placement of stress in “I didn’t say she stole it” versus “I didn’t say she stole it” alters the prominence and interpretation. Such exercises teach learners the peculiarities of spoken English.

Celce-Murcia et al. (2010) suggest integrating prosodic training into consistent speaking practice. Techniques like shadowing where learners repeat after audio recordings advance their awareness of pitch, tone, and natural speech patterns. Incorporating minimal pair exercises (e.g., ship vs. sheep) further enhances their ability to differentiate and produce challenging sounds.

Practical activities for enhancing speaking

Interactive activities provide learners with the opportunity to practice speaking in various contexts. Role-plays, for example, simulate realistic scenarios such as booking a hotel or discussing travel plans. These activities are particularly advantageous for building purposeful language skills. Similarly, debates inspire students to express ideas and construct arguments, fostering critical thinking alongside fluency. Topics such as “Should social media be regulated?” permit learners to engage with relevant problems while practicing convincing language.

Storytelling exercises mature creativity and narrative skills. Asking students to narrate a personal experience or invent a story based on prompts not only enhances their fluency but also reinforces their use of sequencing words and descriptive language. Digital tools like Storybird or Canva can make such tasks more appealing.

Listening-based tasks also contribute significantly to speaking progress. Playing a short podcast and asking learners to summarize or respond to its content helps them connect input with output. Field (2008) states that listening comprehension arranges the foundation for effective spoken interaction by improving learners’ ability to anticipate responses in conversations.

Technology as a tool for speaking practice

Technology provides advanced ways to enhance speaking skills. Platforms including Flipgrid allow students to record and review their speaking performances. This not only inspires self-assessment but also fosters collaborative feedback from peers. Virtual Reality (VR) environments, such as Mondly VR, simulate authentic conversational contexts, enabling learners to practice speaking without geographical or social limitations.

AI-powered language apps, including ELSA Speak, focus on pronunciation and fluency by providing immediate feedback on learners’ spoken production. While these tools are supplementary, they offer a suitable means for students to practice speaking outside the classroom, reinforcing the skills mastered during lessons.

Feedback and assessment

Effective feedback is essential for speaking improvement. Harmer (2007) emphasizes that feedback should be constructive, focusing on communication effectiveness rather than punishing minor grammatical errors. Peer feedback, when organized through rubrics, promotes cooperative learning and allows learners to appreciate diverse speaking styles.

Recording speaking tasks is an additional valuable strategy. When students review their recordings, they can recognize areas of strength and improvement. Dornyei (2001) highlights the motivational aspect of such practices, as learners can track their progress over time, boosting their confidence and sense of achievement.

Conclusion

Enhancing speaking skills for B1-B2 level learners involves a mixture of theoretical insight, practical strategies, and consistent practice. By prioritizing fluency, expanding vocabulary, and integrating pronunciation exercises, teachers can address the unique challenges of intermediate learners. Incorporating technology and fostering an encouraging environment further allows students to become confident communicators. Language learning is an ongoing process that succeeds on communication and real-life application. For both teachers and learners, the journey to proficiency in speaking is as rewarding as the destination.

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